

BIOCHEMICAL INDICATORS OF EXPERIMENTAL NEPHROLITHIASIS IN RATS DEPENDING ON INDIVIDUAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE NERVOUS SYSTEM

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Relevance. The prevalence and incidence of kidney stones have been steadily increasing in recent years. Current data indicate that nephrolithiasis is associated with considerable morbidity, including chronic kidney disease and end-stage renal disease, as well as a significantly elevated risk of cardiovascular complications. Therefore, risk stratification—particularly in high-risk patients—is mandatory when treating kidney stone disease [3]. Nephrolithiasis is a highly prevalent condition that predominantly affects individuals of working age, imposing a substantial economic burden on healthcare systems [2]. The burden of urolithiasis has shown clear regional differences in its distribution over the past three decades. Authors have noted that the incidence of urolithiasis is associated with age distribution, which has remained relatively stable over the past 30 years, with the 40–60-year age group among both men and women being most susceptible [4].

Objective. To study the features of early biochemical indicators of experimental nephrolithiasis in rats, depending on the individual characteristics of the nervous system.

Materials and Methods. The experiments were carried out on 50 white outbred male rats of a mixed population with an initial body weight of 180–200 g, maintained under standard vivarium conditions with a laboratory diet. The study was conducted in accordance with ethical principles of animal handling, consistent with the European Convention for the Protection of Vertebrate Animals Used for Experimental and Other Scientific Purposes (CETS No. 123).

The widely used ethylene glycol model of urolithiasis was applied (administration of 1% ethylene glycol solution in drinking water for 21 days) to induce experimental oxalate nephrolithiasis. Ethylene glycol is slowly oxidized in the body to form oxalic acid, which is then excreted by the kidneys. This model is widely recognized and adequately reproduces human nephrolithiasis [1].

Results and Discussion. The results of biochemical blood parameters obtained after the 21-day experimental period are presented in Table 1. The analysis revealed significant differences in enzyme levels depending on the presence of nephrolithiasis and the severity of emotional stress. Thus, in groups with high and low emotional stress, alanine aminotransferase (ALT) activity was reduced, amounting to 32.88 and 36.37 U/L, respectively. Such a decrease in enzyme activity compared to control values may indicate that the emotional state of animals, along with related hormonal changes, exerts a marked influence on liver functional activity and metabolic processes.

Of particular interest are the findings concerning alkaline phosphatase (ALP). In the group with low emotional stress, the ALP level reached 90.21 U/L, reflecting a moderate increase in activity. However, the most pronounced changes were observed in the nephrolithiasis group with high emotional stress, where ALP activity reached 264.12 U/L. This significant elevation may reflect not only structural and functional alterations in the liver but also profound metabolic shifts associated with stone formation and chronic stress exposure.

In the nephrolithiasis group with low emotional stress, ALP activity also increased, reaching 230.90 U/L. Although somewhat lower than in the high-stress group, this value still substantially exceeded the levels observed in animals without pathology. The greatest differences were noted in groups with pronounced emotional stress, supporting the conclusion that biochemical disturbances are influenced not only by the pathological process of nephrolithiasis itself but also by stress-induced hormonal changes. These results confirm the close relationship between the emotional-hormonal status of the organism and the severity of biochemical abnormalities.

Conclusions:

1. In the group of highly emotional rats with experimental nephrolithiasis, increases in ALP, LDH, and AST were observed compared with low-emotional rats.

A marked elevation of blood urea in highly emotional rats indicates that the progression of nephrolithiasis is more pronounced in this group compared with low-emotional animals

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